

APPENDIX

Appendix 1. Research Questionnaire

Please answer the questions below by ticking () in the column provided in the space provided according to the answer that best represents you.

1. Email Responden :
2. Do you work or have experience working in the Oil & Gas or Petrochemical Industry? : () Yes () No
3. How long have you been working?

(1) 3 – 6 years	(2) 7 – 10 years
(3) 11 – 13 years	(4) 14 years and above
4. Yor Gender? : (1) Female (2) Male

Customer Relationship (CRE)

No.	Question	Evaluation				
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1.	The use of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) as a business approach aims to build good relationships with customers and stakeholders to increase business operational efficiency.					
2.	Customer delight and engagement are becoming important elements for marketing to focus on as customer experience and customers become more empowered than ever.					
3.	Customers are actively involved in organizational culture development.					
4.	Customers frequently give us feedback on quality and delivery performance.					

No.	Question	Evaluation				
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
5.	A culture of continuous improvement, where employees are encouraged to identify important to recognize and Company reward employees for their contributions to lean initiatives.					

Human Resource Practices (HRP)

No.	Question	Evaluation				
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1.	Human Resources Practices contribute to enhancing a firm environmental sustainability.					
2.	Environmental and social aspects are influenced by human resource practices.					
3.	The environmental sustainability performance affected by human resources practices due to employee tacit knowledge on create idea of environmental friendly products.					
4.	An important strategy under human resources practices to gain better understanding of customer and market demand in order to improve social performance.					
5.	An organization affected by human resources practices through control of productivity, quality and rate of innovation, employee turnover rates.					

Manufacturing Planning and Control (MPC)

No.	Question	Evaluation				
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1.	Manufacturing performance is measured differently depending on the objectives and suitability of the research.					
2.	Lean manufacturing practices have enabled manufacturing organizations to achieve more with less cost.					
3.	Industries that follow sustainability as a goal of implementing manufacturing operations require immediate changes to manufacturing planning and control systems.					
4.	Proper planning and control can increase transparency by paying attention to correction rather than prevention.					
5.	The manufacturing planning and control practices have direct effect toward environmental, economic, and social sustainability performance.					

Process and Equipment (PEQ)

No.	Question	Evaluation				
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1.	By using process practices and equipment, eliminating extra processing and unnecessary use including energy and materials.					

No.	Question	Evaluation				
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
2.	Process and equipment practices were significant effect on sustainability performance.					
3.	Extra processing is recognized as one of the wastes under the seven wastes.					
4.	The lean manufacturing method is one way to create added value for industries.					
5.	Processes and equipment will improve the Industry's sustainability performance.					

Supplier Relationship (SRE)

No.	Question	Evaluation				
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1.	Suppliers are directly involved in the new product development process.					
2.	Establish the long-term relationship with our suppliers.					
3.	The main supplier delivers to the manufacture on a just-in-time (JIT) basis.					
4.	Supplier relationship management can be considered as an approach to influencing supplier behavior in improving operational functions.					
5.	Supplier relationship management can be considered as an approach to influencing supplier behavior and influencing sustainability practices.					

Organizational Culture (OCU)

No.	Question	Evaluation				
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1.	Developing an organizational culture will improve company performance with effective teamwork and successful implementation of green lean.					
2.	Lean manufacturing practices are critical and should be implemented throughout the organization.					
3.	Generally, most manufacturing organizations have a policy of disclosing relevant information about their organization.					
4.	Most organizations consider sustainability to strengthen placement and become competitive.					
5.	The lean manufacturing method is a way for producers to maintain their organization..					
6.	Organizational values usually focus on assessing and measuring organizational culture.					
7.	Organizational culture can assist or resist adapting lean practices.					

Sustainable Performance (SPE)

No.	Question	Evaluation				
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1.	Stakeholders and regulatory agencies pressure manufacturing industries to be more sustainable due to the warnings concerning global warming and social issues.					
2.	Relationship between lean manufacturing practices and sustainability is due to the important role of lean manufacturing practices.					
3.	Collaboration with suppliers, customers, industry associations, and research institutions accelerates the implementation of lean and green practices and creates a supportive ecosystem.					
4.	Human resource practices positively impact sustainable performance.					
5.	The green lean manufacturing concept focuses on industrial activities that lead to sustainability.					
6.	Sustainability performance is measured according to research objectives and suitability.					
7.	Lean manufacturing can contribute to sustainability in manufacturing organizations.					

Appendix 2. Tabulation Questionnaire Data Customer Relationship

Respondent	Gender	EXP	CRE1	CRE2	CRE3	CRE4	CRE5	CRE
R1	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R2	2	2	4	4	5	5	5	23
R3	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R4	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R5	2	2	5	4	4	4	5	22
R6	1	3	5	4	4	5	5	23
R7	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R8	2	2	5	4	5	5	4	23
R9	2	2	5	5	4	4	4	22
R10	2	1	4	5	5	4	4	22
R11	2	2	3	4	3	4	4	18
R12	1	3	5	4	4	4	4	21
R13	2	3	5	5	5	5	4	24
R14	1	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R15	1	2	5	5	4	4	4	22
R16	2	1	4	5	5	5	5	24
R17	2	2	5	4	4	4	4	21
R18	2	3	5	4	4	5	4	22
R19	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R20	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R21	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R22	2	1	5	5	5	5	5	25
R23	2	2	5	5	5	5	4	24
R24	1	3	4	3	3	4	4	18
R25	2	3	5	4	5	5	4	23
R26	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R27	1	2	5	4	5	5	4	23
R28	1	1	5	4	5	5	4	23
R29	2	2	4	4	4	5	4	21
R30	2	3	4	5	5	4	4	22
R31	1	2	5	4	4	5	4	22
R32	1	2	3	3	4	4	4	18
R33	2	3	5	4	4	4	4	21
R34	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R35	1	1	4	5	4	4	4	21
R36	2	2	4	5	4	5	4	22
R37	2	1	4	4	5	4	4	21
R38	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20

Respondent	Gender	EXP	CRE1	CRE2	CRE3	CRE4	CRE5	CRE
R39	2	3	5	5	4	5	4	23
R40	2	3	5	5	5	4	4	23
R41	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R42	1	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R43	1	1	5	4	5	5	4	23
R44	2	2	4	5	5	4	5	23
R45	2	3	4	4	5	4	5	22
R46	1	3	5	5	4	5	4	23
R47	2	3	5	5	5	5	4	24
R48	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R49	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R50	1	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R51	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R52	2	3	5	4	5	4	4	22
R53	1	4	4	4	5	4	4	21
R54	2	3	5	4	5	5	4	23
R55	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R56	2	2	4	5	4	4	5	22
R57	1	1	4	4	5	4	5	22
R58	2	2	4	5	4	4	5	22
R59	2	3	4	3	4	4	4	19
R60	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R61	2	2	4	4	4	4	5	21
R62	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R63	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R64	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R65	1	3	4	5	5	4	4	22
R66	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R67	2	3	4	5	4	4	5	22
R68	2	2	4	3	3	4	3	17
R69	2	2	4	5	4	4	4	21
R70	2	1	5	5	4	4	4	22
R71	2	2	5	4	4	4	4	21
R72	2	3	5	5	5	5	4	24
R73	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R74	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R75	1	3	4	4	4	4	5	21
R76	2	2	4	5	4	4	4	21
R77	2	2	5	5	4	4	4	22
R78	2	1	4	5	4	4	4	21

Respondent	Gender	EXP	CRE1	CRE2	CRE3	CRE4	CRE5	CRE
R79	2	2	5	5	5	5	4	24
R80	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R81	1	1	4	5	4	4	4	21
R82	1	2	3	4	3	3	3	16
R83	2	2	5	4	4	4	4	21
R84	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R85	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R86	2	2	5	4	5	5	4	23
R87	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R88	2	1	4	5	4	4	4	21
R89	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R90	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R91	2	2	4	5	5	5	5	24
R92	2	2	4	5	4	4	4	21
R93	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R94	2	2	5	5	4	4	4	22
R95	2	2	5	4	4	4	4	21
R96	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R97	1	2	5	5	5	4	4	23
R98	2	3	4	4	5	4	4	21
R99	2	2	5	5	4	5	4	23
R100	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R101	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R102	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R103	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R104	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R105	2	2	5	4	4	4	5	22
R106	1	3	5	4	5	5	5	24
R107	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R108	2	2	5	4	5	5	4	23
R109	2	3	5	5	4	4	4	22
R110	2	2	4	5	5	4	4	22
R111	2	2	4	4	5	4	4	21
R112	1	1	5	4	4	4	4	21
R113	2	2	3	4	3	3	3	16
R114	1	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R115	2	2	5	5	4	4	4	22
R116	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R117	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R118	2	2	5	4	4	5	4	22

Respondent	Gender	EXP	CRE1	CRE2	CRE3	CRE4	CRE5	CRE
R119	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R120	2	1	5	5	5	5	5	25
R121	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R122	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R123	2	2	5	5	5	5	4	24
R124	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R125	2	3	4	4	5	5	4	22
R126	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R127	2	2	5	4	5	5	4	23
R128	2	1	5	4	5	5	4	23
R129	2	2	3	2	3	3	3	14
R130	2	3	4	5	5	4	4	22
R131	1	2	5	4	4	5	4	22
R132	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R133	2	2	5	4	4	4	4	21
R134	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R135	1	2	4	5	4	4	4	21
R136	2	2	5	5	4	5	4	23
R137	2	1	4	4	5	4	4	21
R138	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R139	2	3	5	5	4	5	4	23
R140	2	2	5	4	4	4	4	21
R141	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R142	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R143	2	2	3	4	4	3	3	17
R144	2	2	4	5	5	4	5	23
R145	2	1	4	4	5	4	5	22
R146	2	2	5	5	4	5	4	23
R147	2	3	5	5	5	5	4	24
R148	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R149	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R150	1	3	5	4	4	4	4	21
R151	2	3	5	5	4	5	5	24
R152	2	2	4	4	5	4	4	21
R153	2	3	4	4	5	4	4	21

Appendix 3. Tabulation Questionnaire Data Human Resource Practices

Respondent	Gender	EXP	HRP1	HRP2	HRP3	HRP4	HRP5	HRP
R1	2	3	5	4	4	4	4	21
R2	2	2	4	5	5	4	5	23
R3	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R4	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R5	2	2	4	4	3	4	4	19
R6	1	3	5	4	5	5	5	24
R7	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R8	2	2	4	5	4	5	4	22
R9	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R10	2	1	4	4	4	5	5	22
R11	2	2	4	5	5	4	3	21
R12	1	3	4	5	5	4	4	22
R13	2	3	4	5	5	4	4	22
R14	1	2	4	4	4	4	3	19
R15	1	2	4	5	4	4	4	21
R16	2	1	5	5	5	5	5	25
R17	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R18	2	3	5	5	5	4	4	23
R19	2	3	4	4	5	5	5	23
R20	1	2	5	5	5	4	3	22
R21	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R22	2	1	5	5	4	4	4	22
R23	2	2	5	5	4	5	5	24
R24	1	3	4	4	4	5	3	20
R25	2	3	5	5	5	5	4	24
R26	2	2	4	4	5	4	4	21
R27	1	2	4	5	5	4	5	23
R28	1	1	4	4	5	4	5	22
R29	2	2	5	5	4	4	5	23
R30	2	3	5	5	4	4	5	23
R31	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R32	1	2	3	3	4	5	4	19
R33	2	3	4	4	4	5	4	21
R34	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R35	1	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R36	2	2	5	5	5	4	4	23
R37	2	1	4	5	5	4	4	22
R38	2	2	4	5	5	4	4	22

R39	2	3	4	5	5	4	5	23
R40	2	3	4	4	5	5	4	22
R41	2	2	4	4	5	5	4	22
R42	1	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R43	1	1	4	5	4	5	4	22
R44	2	2	4	4	4	4	5	21
R45	2	3	5	5	5	4	4	23
R46	1	3	4	4	4	4	5	21
R47	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R48	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R49	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R50	1	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R51	2	2	5	5	5	5	4	24
R52	2	3	4	4	3	4	3	18
R53	1	4	4	5	5	4	4	22
R54	2	3	5	5	5	5	4	24
R55	2	2	4	3	3	3	3	16
R56	2	2	4	4	4	4	5	21
R57	1	1	4	4	4	4	5	21
R58	2	2	4	5	5	5	5	24
R59	2	3	4	4	4	3	3	18
R60	2	3	5	5	5	4	4	23
R61	2	2	5	4	4	4	5	22
R62	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R63	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R64	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R65	1	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R66	2	2	4	4	4	5	5	22
R67	2	3	5	4	4	5	5	23
R68	2	2	4	5	3	4	4	20
R69	2	2	4	4	4	5	5	22
R70	2	1	4	4	4	5	5	22
R71	2	2	4	4	4	5	4	21
R72	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R73	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R74	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R75	1	3	4	4	4	4	3	19
R76	2	2	5	4	4	5	4	22
R77	2	2	4	4	4	4	5	21
R78	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R79	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R80	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	20

R81	1	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R82	1	2	3	3	3	3	4	16
R83	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R84	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R85	2	3	4	4	4	4	5	21
R86	2	2	4	5	5	4	5	23
R87	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R88	2	1	4	5	5	4	4	22
R89	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R90	2	3	4	4	5	5	5	23
R91	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R92	2	2	4	4	4	4	5	21
R93	2	3	5	4	4	5	4	22
R94	2	2	4	5	5	5	5	24
R95	2	2	4	4	4	4	5	21
R96	2	1	4	4	4	4	5	21
R97	1	2	4	5	5	4	5	23
R98	2	3	4	5	5	5	5	24
R99	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R100	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R101	2	3	4	4	5	5	4	22
R102	2	2	4	5	5	4	5	23
R103	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R104	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R105	2	2	4	4	5	4	5	22
R106	1	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R107	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R108	2	2	5	5	4	5	5	24
R109	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R110	2	2	4	4	4	5	5	22
R111	2	2	4	5	4	4	4	21
R112	1	1	4	4	5	4	4	21
R113	2	2	3	3	3	3	3	15
R114	1	3	4	4	4	4	5	21
R115	2	2	4	5	4	4	4	21
R116	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R117	2	3	4	5	4	5	5	23
R118	2	2	4	5	4	4	5	22
R119	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R120	2	1	5	5	5	5	5	25
R121	2	2	4	5	4	3	4	20
R122	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25

R123	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R124	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R125	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R126	2	2	4	4	5	4	4	21
R127	2	2	4	5	4	4	5	22
R128	2	1	4	4	5	4	4	21
R129	2	2	3	4	4	3	3	17
R130	2	3	5	5	4	4	5	23
R131	1	2	4	4	5	5	4	22
R132	2	2	5	5	4	4	5	23
R133	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R134	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R135	1	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R136	2	2	3	4	4	3	4	18
R137	2	1	4	5	4	5	5	23
R138	2	2	4	5	4	4	5	22
R139	2	3	4	5	4	4	5	22
R140	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R141	2	2	4	4	5	4	4	21
R142	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R143	2	2	4	4	4	3	4	19
R144	2	2	4	4	5	5	4	22
R145	2	1	5	5	4	5	5	24
R146	2	2	5	4	4	4	4	21
R147	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R148	2	2	4	3	4	4	4	19
R149	2	3	5	4	4	4	4	21
R150	1	3	4	4	5	4	4	21
R151	2	3	5	4	5	5	5	24
R152	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R153	2	3	4	4	3	3	3	17

Appendix 4. Tabulation Questionnaire Manufacturing Planning and Control

Respondent	Gender	EXP	MPC1	MPC2	MPC3	MPC4	MPC5	MPC
R1	2	3	4	4	4	5	5	22
R2	2	2	5	5	4	5	5	24
R3	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R4	2	1	5	4	4	4	5	22
R5	2	2	4	4	4	5	4	21
R6	1	3	3	3	3	4	3	16
R7	2	3	5	3	3	5	4	20
R8	2	2	5	3	4	5	5	22
R9	2	2	4	3	4	5	5	21
R10	2	1	4	4	4	5	5	22
R11	2	2	4	4	4	4	5	21
R12	1	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R13	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R14	1	2	4	5	5	5	4	23
R15	1	2	4	5	4	4	4	21
R16	2	1	4	5	4	4	5	22
R17	2	2	5	4	4	3	5	21
R18	2	3	5	4	4	3	5	21
R19	2	3	5	4	4	4	5	22
R20	1	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R21	2	2	5	5	5	5	4	24
R22	2	1	3	5	5	5	5	23
R23	2	2	3	5	4	5	5	22
R24	1	3	4	4	4	4	5	21
R25	2	3	4	4	4	4	5	21
R26	2	2	3	4	4	4	4	19
R27	1	2	3	4	4	4	5	20
R28	1	1	3	4	4	5	4	20
R29	2	2	4	5	5	5	5	24
R30	2	3	4	5	4	4	5	22
R31	1	2	4	5	4	4	5	22
R32	1	2	3	4	3	3	4	17
R33	2	3	5	4	4	4	4	21
R34	2	2	4	4	4	4	5	21
R35	1	1	5	5	4	4	4	22
R36	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R37	2	1	4	4	4	5	5	22
R38	2	2	5	5	4	5	4	23

Respondent	Gender	EXP	MPC1	MPC2	MPC3	MPC4	MPC5	MPC
R39	2	3	5	5	5	4	4	23
R40	2	3	5	5	5	4	4	23
R41	2	2	5	5	5	5	4	24
R42	1	2	4	4	4	4	3	19
R43	1	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R44	2	2	5	5	4	5	5	24
R45	2	3	5	4	4	5	5	23
R46	1	3	4	4	4	4	5	21
R47	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R48	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R49	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R50	1	1	5	5	5	4	4	23
R51	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R52	2	3	4	5	5	5	5	24
R53	1	4	3	4	4	4	4	19
R54	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R55	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R56	2	2	5	5	5	4	4	23
R57	1	1	4	3	3	3	4	17
R58	2	2	4	4	5	4	5	22
R59	2	3	4	4	5	5	5	23
R60	2	3	4	4	5	5	4	22
R61	2	2	3	4	4	4	4	19
R62	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R63	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R64	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R65	1	3	4	5	5	4	5	23
R66	2	2	5	5	5	4	5	24
R67	2	3	4	4	4	3	4	19
R68	2	2	4	5	4	4	4	21
R69	2	2	5	5	4	5	5	24
R70	2	1	4	5	4	4	5	22
R71	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R72	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R73	2	2	4	4	4	4	3	19
R74	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R75	1	3	4	5	5	5	5	24
R76	2	2	4	5	4	4	5	22
R77	2	2	4	5	4	4	5	22
R78	2	1	4	4	5	4	4	21

Respondent	Gender	EXP	MPC1	MPC2	MPC3	MPC4	MPC5	MPC
R79	2	2	4	4	5	5	5	23
R80	2	3	3	4	4	4	4	19
R81	1	1	5	4	5	4	4	22
R82	1	2	4	3	3	3	3	16
R83	2	2	5	5	5	4	4	23
R84	1	2	5	5	5	4	5	24
R85	2	3	4	4	4	3	5	20
R86	2	2	3	3	4	4	3	17
R87	2	2	4	5	5	5	5	24
R88	2	1	4	4	5	4	4	21
R89	2	2	4	4	4	3	3	18
R90	2	3	4	4	4	5	4	21
R91	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R92	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R93	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R94	2	2	5	4	5	5	5	24
R95	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R96	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R97	1	2	4	4	5	4	4	21
R98	2	3	5	4	5	5	5	24
R99	2	2	5	4	5	4	5	23
R100	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R101	2	3	4	4	4	3	3	18
R102	2	2	5	5	4	4	4	22
R103	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R104	2	1	3	4	4	4	4	19
R105	2	2	5	4	4	4	4	21
R106	1	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R107	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R108	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R109	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R110	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R111	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R112	1	1	5	4	4	4	4	21
R113	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R114	1	3	4	4	5	5	4	22
R115	2	2	4	4	4	4	3	19
R116	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R117	2	3	4	4	4	5	4	21
R118	2	2	4	4	5	4	4	21

Respondent	Gender	EXP	MPC1	MPC2	MPC3	MPC4	MPC5	MPC
R119	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R120	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R121	2	2	5	4	5	5	5	24
R122	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R123	2	2	4	5	5	5	5	24
R124	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R125	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R126	2	2	5	4	4	5	4	22
R127	2	2	4	5	4	5	5	23
R128	2	1	4	4	4	4	5	21
R129	2	2	3	3	4	3	3	16
R130	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R131	1	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R132	2	2	5	5	5	5	4	24
R133	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R134	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R135	1	2	4	5	4	5	5	23
R136	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R137	2	1	4	4	4	5	4	21
R138	2	2	5	4	5	5	4	23
R139	2	3	4	4	5	5	4	22
R140	2	2	4	5	5	5	4	23
R141	2	2	3	4	3	4	4	18
R142	2	3	4	4	3	5	5	21
R143	2	2	4	4	3	4	5	20
R144	2	2	5	5	4	5	5	24
R145	2	1	5	5	4	5	5	24
R146	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R147	2	3	5	5	5	4	4	23
R148	2	2	4	4	5	4	4	21
R149	2	3	4	4	5	4	5	22
R150	1	3	4	4	5	5	5	23
R151	2	3	4	5	5	5	5	24
R152	2	2	3	4	4	4	4	19
R153	2	3	4	5	4	4	5	22

Appendix 5. Tabulation Questionnaire Data Process and Equipment

Respondent	Gender	EXP	PEQ1	PEQ2	PEQ3	PEQ4	PEQ5	PEQ
R1	2	3	5	5	4	4	5	23
R2	2	2	4	5	5	5	4	23
R3	1	2	5	5	5	4	4	23
R4	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R5	2	2	4	5	5	4	4	22
R6	1	3	5	5	4	4	5	23
R7	2	3	4	4	4	4	5	21
R8	2	2	5	4	4	5	5	23
R9	2	2	4	5	5	4	4	22
R10	2	1	5	5	5	5	5	25
R11	2	2	3	4	3	4	4	18
R12	1	3	4	4	5	4	4	21
R13	2	3	5	5	5	4	4	23
R14	1	2	3	4	4	4	3	18
R15	1	2	4	4	4	5	4	21
R16	2	1	3	5	5	5	5	23
R17	2	2	3	3	4	4	4	18
R18	2	3	3	5	4	5	4	21
R19	2	3	3	5	5	5	5	23
R20	1	2	4	5	5	5	5	24
R21	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R22	2	1	4	5	5	5	5	24
R23	2	2	4	4	5	5	5	23
R24	1	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R25	2	3	4	4	5	5	4	22
R26	2	2	3	3	4	5	5	20
R27	1	2	4	4	5	5	4	22
R28	1	1	3	4	4	4	5	20
R29	2	2	4	4	5	3	4	20
R30	2	3	4	5	5	3	5	22
R31	1	2	4	5	5	4	4	22
R32	1	2	4	5	5	4	3	21
R33	2	3	4	5	5	5	4	23
R34	2	2	5	5	4	5	5	24
R35	1	1	3	4	3	4	4	18
R36	2	2	3	4	4	4	4	19
R37	2	1	4	3	4	4	4	19
R38	2	2	4	5	4	5	5	23

Respondent	Gender	EXP	PEQ1	PEQ2	PEQ3	PEQ4	PEQ5	PEQ
R39	2	3	4	5	5	5	5	24
R40	2	3	4	4	5	5	5	23
R41	2	2	4	4	5	5	4	22
R42	1	2	4	4	5	5	4	22
R43	1	1	4	4	5	5	4	22
R44	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R45	2	3	4	4	5	4	4	21
R46	1	3	5	4	5	4	4	22
R47	2	3	5	5	4	4	5	23
R48	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R49	2	2	5	4	5	5	5	24
R50	1	1	4	4	4	5	5	22
R51	2	2	5	4	4	4	5	22
R52	2	3	4	4	4	4	5	21
R53	1	4	5	4	4	5	5	23
R54	2	3	5	5	4	5	5	24
R55	2	2	4	3	3	4	4	18
R56	2	2	5	5	5	5	4	24
R57	1	1	3	4	3	3	3	16
R58	2	2	5	4	4	5	5	23
R59	2	3	4	3	3	3	4	17
R60	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R61	2	2	5	5	4	4	5	23
R62	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R63	2	1	3	4	3	4	4	18
R64	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R65	1	3	5	5	4	5	5	24
R66	2	2	5	4	5	5	5	24
R67	2	3	5	4	5	4	5	23
R68	2	2	4	4	3	3	4	18
R69	2	2	5	5	4	4	5	23
R70	2	1	5	4	5	4	4	22
R71	2	2	4	4	4	5	4	21
R72	2	3	5	4	5	4	4	22
R73	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R74	2	2	5	5	4	5	5	24
R75	1	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R76	2	2	4	4	4	5	5	22
R77	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R78	2	1	4	4	4	5	5	22

Respondent	Gender	EXP	PEQ1	PEQ2	PEQ3	PEQ4	PEQ5	PEQ
R79	2	2	3	3	4	4	4	18
R80	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R81	1	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R82	1	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R83	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R84	1	2	4	4	4	4	5	21
R85	2	3	4	3	4	3	3	17
R86	2	2	4	5	5	4	4	22
R87	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R88	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R89	2	2	5	5	4	4	4	22
R90	2	3	5	4	4	4	5	22
R91	2	2	4	5	5	5	5	24
R92	2	2	5	4	5	4	5	23
R93	2	3	3	4	3	3	4	17
R94	2	2	5	5	4	5	5	24
R95	2	2	5	4	4	4	4	21
R96	2	1	5	4	4	5	5	23
R97	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R98	2	3	5	4	5	4	4	22
R99	2	2	5	5	5	4	5	24
R100	2	2	5	5	4	4	5	23
R101	2	3	5	5	4	4	5	23
R102	2	2	4	5	5	5	4	23
R103	1	2	5	5	5	4	4	23
R104	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R105	2	2	4	5	5	4	4	22
R106	1	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R107	2	2	4	4	4	4	5	21
R108	2	2	5	4	4	5	5	23
R109	2	3	4	3	4	4	4	19
R110	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R111	2	2	3	4	4	4	4	19
R112	1	1	4	4	5	5	4	22
R113	2	2	5	5	5	4	4	23
R114	1	3	4	3	4	4	3	18
R115	2	2	4	4	4	5	4	21
R116	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R117	2	3	4	5	5	4	4	22
R118	2	2	5	4	4	5	4	22

Respondent	Gender	EXP	PEQ1	PEQ2	PEQ3	PEQ4	PEQ5	PEQ
R119	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R120	2	1	5	5	5	4	5	24
R121	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R122	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R123	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R124	1	2	5	4	4	5	4	22
R125	2	3	5	4	4	4	4	21
R126	2	2	5	4	4	4	4	21
R127	2	2	5	4	4	5	5	23
R128	2	1	5	5	4	4	4	22
R129	2	2	3	4	3	4	4	18
R130	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R131	1	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R132	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R133	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R134	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R135	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R136	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R137	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R138	2	2	5	4	5	5	5	24
R139	2	3	5	4	5	5	5	24
R140	2	2	5	4	5	5	5	24
R141	2	2	5	4	5	5	5	24
R142	2	3	4	3	4	4	4	19
R143	2	2	4	3	4	4	3	18
R144	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R145	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R146	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R147	2	3	4	4	5	5	5	23
R148	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R149	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R150	1	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R151	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R152	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R153	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25

Appendix 6. Tabulation Questionnaire Data Supplier Relationship

Respondent	Gender	EXP	SRE1	SRE2	SRE3	SRE4	SRE5	SRE
R1	2	3	4	5	5	4	4	22
R2	2	2	5	5	4	5	4	23
R3	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R4	2	1	4	5	4	4	4	21
R5	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R6	1	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R7	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R8	2	2	4	5	5	4	5	23
R9	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R10	2	1	5	5	5	4	5	24
R11	2	2	3	4	3	3	4	17
R12	1	3	4	4	4	5	5	22
R13	2	3	4	4	4	5	4	21
R14	1	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R15	1	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R16	2	1	5	5	5	5	5	25
R17	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R18	2	3	5	5	4	5	4	23
R19	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R20	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R21	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R22	2	1	5	5	5	5	5	25
R23	2	2	5	4	5	5	5	24
R24	1	3	4	4	3	3	4	18
R25	2	3	5	4	4	5	5	23
R26	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R27	1	2	4	5	5	5	5	24
R28	1	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R29	2	2	4	5	4	4	4	21
R30	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R31	1	2	4	5	4	5	5	23
R32	1	2	3	3	4	4	3	17
R33	2	3	4	4	5	4	4	21
R34	2	2	4	5	5	5	5	24
R35	1	1	4	3	4	4	4	19
R36	2	2	4	4	4	4	5	21
R37	2	1	3	3	3	3	4	16
R38	2	2	3	4	5	4	4	20

Respondent	Gender	EXP	SRE1	SRE2	SRE3	SRE4	SRE5	SRE
R39	2	3	3	4	5	4	4	20
R40	2	3	5	4	5	5	5	24
R41	2	2	4	5	5	5	4	23
R42	1	2	4	5	4	5	4	22
R43	1	1	4	5	4	5	4	22
R44	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R45	2	3	5	5	4	4	3	21
R46	1	3	5	5	4	5	4	23
R47	2	3	4	5	4	4	3	20
R48	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R49	2	2	4	5	5	5	4	23
R50	1	1	4	5	4	5	4	22
R51	2	2	4	4	3	4	4	19
R52	2	3	4	4	4	5	4	21
R53	1	4	5	4	5	5	4	23
R54	2	3	3	4	4	4	4	19
R55	2	2	4	5	5	4	4	22
R56	2	2	4	5	5	4	5	23
R57	1	1	4	3	4	4	4	19
R58	2	2	4	5	4	4	4	21
R59	2	3	4	5	4	4	4	21
R60	2	3	5	5	4	5	5	24
R61	2	2	5	5	5	4	4	23
R62	2	2	3	4	4	3	3	17
R63	2	1	5	4	4	4	4	21
R64	2	2	5	4	4	5	5	23
R65	1	3	4	4	5	4	5	22
R66	2	2	5	5	5	4	5	24
R67	2	3	5	4	5	4	4	22
R68	2	2	4	3	4	3	3	17
R69	2	2	4	5	4	5	4	22
R70	2	1	5	4	5	5	5	24
R71	2	2	4	3	3	4	4	18
R72	2	3	5	5	3	4	5	22
R73	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R74	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R75	1	3	4	4	5	4	5	22
R76	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R77	2	2	5	4	5	4	4	22
R78	2	1	5	5	4	4	4	22

Respondent	Gender	EXP	SRE1	SRE2	SRE3	SRE4	SRE5	SRE
R79	2	2	4	4	4	5	4	21
R80	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R81	1	1	4	5	4	4	3	20
R82	1	2	4	4	3	3	3	17
R83	2	2	5	5	5	4	4	23
R84	1	2	4	5	5	3	3	20
R85	2	3	5	4	5	4	4	22
R86	2	2	4	4	4	5	4	21
R87	2	2	4	4	4	4	5	21
R88	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R89	2	2	4	4	5	4	5	22
R90	2	3	4	4	5	5	4	22
R91	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R92	2	2	5	5	4	4	4	22
R93	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R94	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R95	2	2	4	4	4	5	4	21
R96	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	20
R97	1	2	5	4	4	4	4	21
R98	2	3	5	5	5	4	5	24
R99	2	2	5	5	4	5	5	24
R100	2	2	5	4	5	5	5	24
R101	2	3	4	5	5	4	4	22
R102	2	2	5	5	4	5	4	23
R103	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R104	2	1	4	5	4	4	4	21
R105	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R106	1	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R107	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R108	2	2	4	5	5	4	5	23
R109	2	3	4	5	5	4	4	22
R110	2	2	5	5	5	4	5	24
R111	2	2	4	4	4	5	5	22
R112	1	1	4	4	4	5	5	22
R113	2	2	4	4	4	5	4	21
R114	1	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R115	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R116	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R117	2	3	4	4	4	4	5	21
R118	2	2	5	5	4	5	4	23

Respondent	Gender	EXP	SRE1	SRE2	SRE3	SRE4	SRE5	SRE
R119	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R120	2	1	5	5	5	5	5	25
R121	2	2	4	5	4	4	4	21
R122	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R123	2	2	5	4	5	5	5	24
R124	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R125	2	3	5	4	4	5	5	23
R126	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R127	2	2	4	5	5	4	4	22
R128	2	1	4	4	4	5	4	21
R129	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R130	2	3	4	4	5	4	4	21
R131	1	2	4	5	5	5	5	24
R132	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R133	2	2	4	4	4	4	3	19
R134	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R135	1	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R136	2	2	4	4	4	4	5	21
R137	2	1	4	4	4	4	5	21
R138	2	2	4	4	5	4	4	21
R139	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R140	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	25
R141	2	2	4	4	4	5	4	21
R142	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	20
R143	2	2	4	4	4	5	5	22
R144	2	2	5	4	5	5	5	24
R145	2	1	4	5	4	4	5	22
R146	2	2	5	5	4	5	4	23
R147	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R148	2	2	4	4	4	5	5	22
R149	2	3	4	5	5	5	4	23
R150	1	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R151	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	25
R152	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	20
R153	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	20

Appendix 7. Tabulation Questionnaire Data Organizational Culture

Respondent	Gender	EXP	OCU1	OCU2	OCU3	OCU4	OCU5	OCU6	OCU7	OCU
R1	2	3	4	4	4	4	5	5	5	27
R2	2	2	5	5	5	4	4	4	4	26
R3	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R4	2	1	4	5	4	4	4	4	4	24
R5	2	2	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	25
R6	1	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R7	2	3	4	4	4	4	5	4	4	25
R8	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R9	2	2	4	5	4	4	4	4	4	24
R10	2	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R11	2	2	4	3	3	4	3	4	4	22
R12	1	3	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	25
R13	2	3	5	5	5	5	4	4	5	28
R14	1	2	5	4	4	5	5	4	5	28
R15	1	2	4	5	4	4	4	5	4	25
R16	2	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R17	2	2	5	4	4	4	5	4	4	26
R18	2	3	5	5	4	5	4	4	5	27
R19	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R20	1	2	5	5	5	4	4	4	5	27
R21	2	2	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	29
R22	2	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R23	2	2	4	4	5	4	4	4	4	25
R24	1	3	4	4	3	4	4	4	3	22
R25	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	24
R26	2	2	4	5	4	4	4	4	4	24
R27	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R28	1	1	5	4	4	4	4	5	4	26
R29	2	2	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	29
R30	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R31	1	2	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	24
R32	1	2	3	3	3	4	3	3	3	19
R33	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	24
R34	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R35	1	1	4	4	5	4	4	4	4	25
R36	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R37	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	24
R38	2	2	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	25

Respondent	Gender	EXP	OCU1	OCU2	OCU3	OCU4	OCU5	OCU6	OCU7	OCU
R39	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	28
R40	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R41	2	2	4	5	4	4	4	4	4	24
R42	1	2	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	24
R43	1	1	5	4	4	4	3	4	4	24
R44	2	2	4	4	5	4	5	5	5	28
R45	2	3	4	5	4	4	5	5	4	26
R46	1	3	4	4	4	4	4	5	5	26
R47	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R48	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R49	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	4	5	25
R50	1	1	5	5	5	5	4	4	4	27
R51	2	2	5	4	4	4	4	5	5	27
R52	2	3	4	4	5	4	4	4	4	25
R53	1	4	4	5	4	4	4	5	5	26
R54	2	3	5	5	5	4	4	5	5	28
R55	2	2	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	25
R56	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R57	1	1	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	24
R58	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R59	2	3	4	4	3	4	3	5	4	23
R60	2	3	4	4	4	5	5	4	4	26
R61	2	2	5	5	4	4	4	4	5	26
R62	2	2	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	29
R63	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	24
R64	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R65	1	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R66	2	2	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	29
R67	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R68	2	2	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	23
R69	2	2	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	29
R70	2	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R71	2	2	4	5	5	5	5	4	4	27
R72	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R73	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	24
R74	2	2	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	29
R75	1	3	5	4	3	4	5	3	4	24
R76	2	2	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	26
R77	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	24
R78	2	1	4	5	4	5	4	4	4	25

Respondent	Gender	EXP	OCU1	OCU2	OCU3	OCU4	OCU5	OCU6	OCU7	OCU
R79	2	2	3	4	4	5	3	3	5	23
R80	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	24
R81	1	1	4	5	4	5	4	4	4	25
R82	1	2	3	3	4	3	3	3	4	20
R83	2	2	4	5	5	5	4	4	4	26
R84	1	2	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	26
R85	2	3	5	4	4	5	5	5	5	29
R86	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	5	4	25
R87	2	2	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	26
R88	2	1	4	5	4	5	4	4	5	26
R89	2	2	5	4	4	4	4	5	5	27
R90	2	3	5	4	4	4	5	4	5	27
R91	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	28
R92	2	2	5	5	4	4	4	4	5	26
R93	2	3	5	4	4	4	4	4	5	26
R94	2	2	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	29
R95	2	2	5	5	4	4	4	4	5	26
R96	2	1	5	4	4	4	4	4	5	26
R97	1	2	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	27
R98	2	3	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	29
R99	2	2	5	5	4	5	4	5	5	28
R100	2	2	5	5	5	4	4	5	5	28
R101	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	5	5	26
R102	2	2	5	5	5	4	4	4	4	26
R103	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R104	2	1	4	5	4	4	4	4	4	24
R105	2	2	5	5	4	4	5	5	4	27
R106	1	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R107	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	24
R108	2	2	5	4	5	5	4	5	5	29
R109	2	3	4	5	4	4	4	4	4	24
R110	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R111	2	2	4	4	4	3	4	4	3	22
R112	1	1	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	25
R113	2	2	3	4	3	3	3	4	3	19
R114	1	3	3	4	4	4	3	3	5	22
R115	2	2	4	5	4	4	4	4	4	24
R116	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R117	2	3	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	25
R118	2	2	5	5	4	5	4	4	5	27

Respondent	Gender	EXP	OCU1	OCU2	OCU3	OCU4	OCU5	OCU6	OCU7	OCU
R119	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R120	2	1	5	4	5	4	4	4	5	27
R121	2	2	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	29
R122	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R123	2	2	4	4	5	4	4	4	4	25
R124	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R125	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	5	4	25
R126	2	2	4	5	4	4	4	4	4	24
R127	2	2	5	4	5	4	4	5	5	28
R128	2	1	5	4	4	4	4	5	4	26
R129	2	2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	18
R130	2	3	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	28
R131	1	2	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	24
R132	2	2	4	5	5	5	5	4	5	28
R133	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	24
R134	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R135	1	2	4	4	5	4	4	4	4	25
R136	2	2	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	27
R137	2	1	4	4	4	4	5	5	4	26
R138	2	2	5	5	5	4	5	4	4	27
R139	2	3	5	5	5	5	4	4	4	27
R140	2	2	5	5	5	5	4	4	5	28
R141	2	2	4	5	4	4	4	4	4	24
R142	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	24
R143	2	2	3	4	4	3	5	3	3	21
R144	2	2	4	4	5	4	5	5	5	28
R145	2	1	4	5	4	4	5	5	4	26
R146	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	4	5	25
R147	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	30
R148	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	24
R149	2	3	4	5	5	4	4	4	5	26
R150	1	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	29
R151	2	3	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	29
R152	2	2	4	4	5	4	4	4	4	25
R153	2	3	4	5	4	4	4	5	5	26

Appendix 8. Tabulation Questionnaire Sustainable Performance

Respondent	Gender	EXP	SPE1	SPE2	SPE3	SPE4	SPE5	SPE6	SPE7	SPE
R1	2	3	5	4	4	5	4	5	5	32
R2	2	2	5	5	5	4	5	5	4	33
R3	1	2	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	34
R4	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	5	4	29
R5	2	2	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	30
R6	1	3	5	4	4	5	5	5	5	33
R7	2	3	4	4	4	5	4	4	4	29
R8	2	2	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	34
R9	2	2	5	5	4	4	4	5	5	32
R10	2	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	35
R11	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	28
R12	1	3	4	5	5	4	4	4	4	30
R13	2	3	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	30
R14	1	2	5	3	4	3	4	3	4	26
R15	1	2	4	4	5	4	4	4	4	29
R16	2	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	35
R17	2	2	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	30
R18	2	3	4	4	5	4	5	5	4	31
R19	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	35
R20	1	2	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	34
R21	2	2	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	31
R22	2	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	35
R23	2	2	4	5	5	5	5	4	5	33
R24	1	3	5	4	5	4	4	4	4	30
R25	2	3	4	4	4	4	5	4	4	29
R26	2	2	4	4	4	5	4	4	4	29
R27	1	2	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	34
R28	1	1	4	5	4	4	4	4	4	29
R29	2	2	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	34
R30	2	3	4	5	5	5	4	4	5	32
R31	1	2	5	5	4	4	5	5	5	33
R32	1	2	3	3	4	4	3	3	4	24
R33	2	3	4	3	4	4	3	3	4	25
R34	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	35
R35	1	1	4	4	5	4	4	4	4	29
R36	2	2	4	4	5	5	4	4	4	30
R37	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	28

Respondent	Gender	EXP	SPE1	SPE2	SPE3	SPE4	SPE5	SPE6	SPE7	SPE
R38	2	2	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	31
R39	2	3	4	4	4	5	4	4	4	29
R40	2	3	4	4	5	5	5	5	5	33
R41	2	2	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	27
R42	1	2	3	3	3	4	3	4	4	24
R43	1	1	5	4	5	5	4	5	5	33
R44	2	2	5	5	4	5	5	4	5	33
R45	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	5	4	29
R46	1	3	4	4	5	4	5	5	5	32
R47	2	3	4	4	4	5	5	5	5	32
R48	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	35
R49	2	2	4	5	5	5	4	5	5	33
R50	1	1	4	4	5	5	5	5	5	33
R51	2	2	4	4	4	5	5	5	5	32
R52	2	3	3	4	3	4	4	4	4	26
R53	1	4	4	4	5	5	4	4	4	30
R54	2	3	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	29
R55	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	28
R56	2	2	5	5	5	4	5	5	4	33
R57	1	1	5	5	5	5	3	5	5	33
R58	2	2	4	4	5	5	5	4	4	31
R59	2	3	4	3	4	3	3	4	3	24
R60	2	3	5	5	5	4	5	4	5	33
R61	2	2	5	4	4	5	5	5	5	33
R62	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	35
R63	2	1	4	3	4	4	3	4	4	26
R64	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	35
R65	1	3	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	30
R66	2	2	4	5	5	5	5	5	4	33
R67	2	3	4	5	4	5	5	4	5	32
R68	2	2	4	5	5	4	4	4	5	31
R69	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	5	4	29
R70	2	1	5	5	5	4	5	4	5	33
R71	2	2	4	4	5	4	5	4	4	30
R72	2	3	4	5	4	4	5	5	5	32
R73	2	2	3	4	3	3	4	4	4	25
R74	2	2	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	34
R75	1	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	5	29
R76	2	2	4	4	4	5	4	4	4	29
R77	2	2	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	27

Respondent	Gender	EXP	SPE1	SPE2	SPE3	SPE4	SPE5	SPE6	SPE7	SPE
R78	2	1	4	4	5	5	5	5	4	32
R79	2	2	3	3	4	4	3	4	4	25
R80	2	3	4	3	4	4	4	3	4	26
R81	1	1	4	4	4	4	4	5	4	29
R82	1	2	3	4	3	3	4	4	3	24
R83	2	2	5	4	5	4	5	5	5	33
R84	1	2	4	4	4	5	4	5	5	31
R85	2	3	5	5	4	4	5	4	5	32
R86	2	2	4	5	3	3	4	4	4	27
R87	2	2	4	5	5	4	4	5	4	31
R88	2	1	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	29
R89	2	2	3	4	3	3	4	4	4	25
R90	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	34
R91	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	35
R92	2	2	4	5	4	5	5	5	4	32
R93	2	3	3	5	4	4	4	5	4	29
R94	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	35
R95	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	28
R96	2	1	4	4	5	5	4	4	4	30
R97	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	33
R98	2	3	4	5	4	4	5	5	5	32
R99	2	2	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	34
R100	2	2	5	4	4	5	5	4	5	32
R101	2	3	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	34
R102	2	2	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	34
R103	1	2	5	5	4	4	5	5	5	33
R104	2	1	4	3	3	3	4	5	4	26
R105	2	2	5	5	3	4	4	3	4	28
R106	1	3	5	4	4	5	5	5	5	33
R107	2	2	4	3	3	3	4	4	4	25
R108	2	2	4	4	5	5	5	5	5	33
R109	2	3	5	5	4	4	4	5	5	32
R110	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	35
R111	2	2	4	4	3	4	3	3	4	25
R112	1	1	4	3	5	3	4	4	4	27
R113	2	2	3	3	3	3	3	4	3	22
R114	1	3	3	4	4	4	3	3	4	25
R115	2	2	4	4	5	4	4	4	4	29
R116	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	35
R117	2	3	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	30

Respondent	Gender	EXP	SPE1	SPE2	SPE3	SPE4	SPE5	SPE6	SPE7	SPE
R118	2	2	4	4	5	4	5	5	5	32
R119	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	35
R120	2	1	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	34
R121	2	2	4	4	3	4	4	5	4	28
R122	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	35
R123	2	2	4	5	5	5	5	4	5	33
R124	1	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	35
R125	2	3	4	4	4	4	5	4	4	29
R126	2	2	4	4	4	5	4	4	4	29
R127	2	2	5	5	5	4	4	5	5	33
R128	2	1	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	34
R129	2	2	3	2	3	3	3	3	4	21
R130	2	3	4	5	5	5	4	4	5	32
R131	1	2	4	3	4	4	3	3	5	26
R132	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	35
R133	2	2	4	4	3	4	4	3	4	26
R134	2	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	35
R135	1	2	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	28
R136	2	2	4	3	4	3	3	4	4	25
R137	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	28
R138	2	2	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	31
R139	2	3	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	27
R140	2	2	4	4	5	5	5	5	5	33
R141	2	2	4	4	4	3	4	3	3	25
R142	2	3	3	3	3	4	3	4	3	23
R143	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	28
R144	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	34
R145	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	5	4	29
R146	2	2	4	4	5	4	5	5	4	31
R147	2	3	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	34
R148	2	2	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	27
R149	2	3	4	5	5	5	4	5	5	33
R150	1	3	4	4	5	5	5	5	5	33
R151	2	3	4	4	4	5	5	5	5	32
R152	2	2	4	3	3	4	4	4	4	26
R153	2	3	4	4	5	5	4	4	4	30

Appendix 9. Evaluation of Measurement Models

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
CRE1 ← CRE	0.752	0.749	0.047	15.865	0.000
CRE2 ← CRE	0.732	0.729	0.047	15.674	0.000
CRE3 ← CRE	0.781	0.780	0.037	20.870	0.000
CRE4 ← CRE	0.838	0.837	0.028	30.253	0.000
CRE5 ← CRE	0.761	0.759	0.041	18.389	0.000
HRP1 ← HRP	0.791	0.790	0.034	23.226	0.000
HRP2 ← HRP	0.750	0.750	0.046	16.488	0.000
HRP3 ← HRP	0.715	0.713	0.052	13.789	0.000
HRP4 ← HRP	0.770	0.767	0.050	15.433	0.000
HRP5 ← HRP	0.735	0.734	0.043	17.260	0.000
MPC1 ← MPC	0.713	0.712	0.057	12.510	0.000
MPC2 ← MPC	0.796	0.792	0.042	18.881	0.000
MPC3 ← MPC	0.774	0.773	0.040	19.594	0.000
MPC4 ← MPC	0.703	0.696	0.060	11.670	0.000
MPC5 ← MPC	0.714	0.711	0.053	13.568	0.000
OCU1 ← OCU	0.781	0.780	0.038	20.800	0.000
OCU2 ← OCU	0.739	0.737	0.045	16.260	0.000
OCU3 ← OCU	0.735	0.732	0.043	17.142	0.000
OCU4 ← OCU	0.794	0.793	0.040	19.787	0.000
OCU5 ← OCU	0.757	0.753	0.050	15.214	0.000
OCU6 ← OCU	0.733	0.733	0.045	16.224	0.000
OCU7 ← OCU	0.764	0.762	0.045	17.073	0.000
PEQ1 ← PEQ	0.729	0.728	0.059	12.281	0.000
PEQ2 ← PEQ	0.735	0.734	0.046	16.038	0.000
PEQ3 ← PEQ	0.701	0.697	0.061	11.549	0.000
PEQ4 ← PEQ	0.701	0.696	0.060	11.743	0.000
PEQ5 ← PEQ	0.778	0.778	0.039	19.974	0.000
SPE1 ← SPE	0.721	0.718	0.047	15.481	0.000
SPE2 ← SPE	0.742	0.740	0.042	17.563	0.000
SPE3 ← SPE	0.709	0.707	0.047	15.130	0.000
SPE4 ← SPE	0.733	0.731	0.041	17.794	0.000
SPE5 ← SPE	0.825	0.825	0.032	25.512	0.000
SPE6 ← SPE	0.724	0.725	0.041	17.513	0.000
SPE7 ← SPE	0.825	0.826	0.029	28.920	0.000
SRE1 ← SRE	0.795	0.793	0.033	24.280	0.000
SRE2 ← SRE	0.723	0.724	0.046	15.659	0.000
SRE3 ← SRE	0.750	0.749	0.044	16.937	0.000
SRE4 ← SRE	0.708	0.701	0.058	12.282	0.000
SRE5 ← SRE	0.732	0.730	0.046	15.774	0.000

Appendix 10. Level of Reliability and Convergent Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
CRE	0.831	0.832	0.881	0.598
HRP	0.809	0.815	0.867	0.566
MPC	0.795	0.800	0.859	0.549
OCU	0.876	0.877	0.904	0.574
PEQ	0.781	0.788	0.850	0.532
SPE	0.874	0.881	0.903	0.571
SRE	0.798	0.805	0.860	0.551

Appendix 11. Cross Loading

Indicators	CRE	HRP	MPC	PEQ	SRE	OCU	SPE
CRE1	0.752	0.479	0.261	0.306	0.388	0.449	0.464
CRE2	0.732	0.496	0.390	0.437	0.402	0.559	0.523
CRE3	0.781	0.606	0.309	0.347	0.392	0.482	0.510
CRE4	0.838	0.680	0.326	0.318	0.382	0.481	0.540
CRE5	0.761	0.544	0.275	0.319	0.440	0.501	0.551
HRP1	0.664	0.791	0.418	0.236	0.438	0.535	0.558
HRP2	0.514	0.750	0.352	0.297	0.235	0.443	0.450
HRP3	0.514	0.715	0.225	0.298	0.277	0.402	0.397
HRP4	0.522	0.770	0.339	0.357	0.350	0.467	0.501
HRP5	0.508	0.735	0.208	0.398	0.405	0.561	0.533
MPC1	0.266	0.284	0.713	0.277	0.176	0.394	0.316
MPC2	0.297	0.328	0.796	0.353	0.224	0.405	0.342
MPC3	0.335	0.304	0.774	0.262	0.278	0.459	0.324
MPC4	0.313	0.264	0.703	0.284	0.226	0.305	0.233
MPC5	0.296	0.339	0.714	0.224	0.256	0.368	0.388
PEQ1	0.276	0.293	0.305	0.729	0.296	0.422	0.353
PEQ2	0.378	0.358	0.239	0.735	0.335	0.377	0.368
PEQ3	0.319	0.300	0.278	0.701	0.411	0.364	0.311
PEQ4	0.260	0.231	0.277	0.701	0.272	0.335	0.275
PEQ5	0.391	0.343	0.278	0.778	0.296	0.467	0.408
SRE1	0.393	0.378	0.215	0.312	0.795	0.438	0.530
SRE2	0.376	0.321	0.301	0.319	0.723	0.463	0.501
SRE3	0.419	0.321	0.198	0.397	0.750	0.476	0.497
SRE4	0.405	0.291	0.177	0.288	0.708	0.261	0.324

Indicators	CRE	HRP	MPC	PEQ	SRE	OCU	SPE
SRE5	0.344	0.400	0.262	0.296	0.732	0.429	0.409
OCU1	0.489	0.497	0.330	0.447	0.405	0.781	0.581
OCU2	0.416	0.429	0.416	0.409	0.451	0.739	0.491
OCU3	0.590	0.520	0.439	0.470	0.518	0.735	0.560
OCU4	0.460	0.488	0.468	0.366	0.398	0.794	0.552
OCU5	0.437	0.490	0.392	0.315	0.418	0.757	0.545
OCU6	0.449	0.533	0.394	0.430	0.387	0.733	0.506
OCU7	0.549	0.472	0.359	0.439	0.450	0.764	0.570
SPE1	0.534	0.495	0.276	0.389	0.468	0.539	0.721
SPE2	0.470	0.488	0.278	0.298	0.398	0.515	0.742
SPE3	0.399	0.373	0.349	0.256	0.365	0.459	0.709
SPE4	0.506	0.499	0.323	0.436	0.379	0.526	0.733
SPE5	0.542	0.608	0.388	0.466	0.567	0.655	0.825
SPE6	0.473	0.411	0.400	0.324	0.495	0.551	0.724
SPE7	0.604	0.559	0.312	0.321	0.583	0.536	0.825

Appendix 12. Fornell Lacker

	CRE	HRP	MPC	PEQ	SRE	OCU	SPE
CRE	0.773						
HRP	0.727	0.753					
MPC	0.406	0.412	0.741				
PEQ	0.449	0.422	0.376	0.729			
SRE	0.520	0.463	0.314	0.438	0.742		
OCU	0.642	0.647	0.528	0.544	0.572	0.758	
SPE	0.672	0.656	0.439	0.476	0.624	0.719	0.756

Appendix 13. Heterotrait Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

	CRE	HRP	MPC	PEQ	SRE	OCU	SPE
CRE							
HRP	0.880						
MPC	0.498	0.508					
PEQ	0.549	0.525	0.480				
SRE	0.638	0.561	0.388	0.554			
OCU	0.745	0.758	0.625	0.648	0.662		
SPE	0.780	0.763	0.521	0.563	0.718	0.816	

Appendix 14. Hypothesis Test

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
CRE → OCU	0.177	0.165	0.079	2.236	0.026
HRP → OCU	0.253	0.252	0.083	3.042	0.002
MPC → OCU	0.215	0.222	0.069	3.096	0.002
PEQ → OCU	0.182	0.187	0.069	2.652	0.008
SRE → OCU	0.216	0.219	0.060	3.583	0.000
OCU → SPE	0.306	0.299	0.075	4.056	0.000
CRE → SPE	0.191	0.194	0.088	2.164	0.031
HRP → SPE	0.179	0.173	0.082	2.187	0.029
MPC → SPE	0.040	0.042	0.065	0.609	0.543
PEQ → SPE	0.026	0.028	0.072	0.364	0.716
SRE → SPE	0.242	0.252	0.065	3.736	0.000

Appendix 15. R Square Interpretation Value (R²)

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
OCU	0.614	0.601
SPE	0.647	0.633

Appendix 16. Predictive Relevance (Q²)

	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE or SSO)
OCU	1.071.000	708.676	0.338
SPE	1.071.000	689.179	0.357

Appendix 17. Effect Size (F²)

	OCU	SPE
CRE	0.034	0.041
HRP	0.074	0.038
MPC	0.092	0.003
PEQ	0.060	0.001
SRE	0.080	0.103
OCU		0.103

Appendix 18. GoF Index

Variables	Indicators	Outer Loading	Communality	Variable	R Square	GoF Index
Customer Relationship	CRE1 ← CRE	0,752	0,566	OCU	0,614	
	CRE2 ← CRE	0,732	0,536	SPE	0,647	
	CRE3 ← CRE	0,781	0,610			
	CRE4 ← CRE	0,838	0,702			
	CRE5 ← CRE	0,761	0,579			
Human Resource Practices	HRP1 ← HRP	0,791	0,626			
	HRP2 ← HRP	0,75	0,563			
	HRP3 ← HRP	0,715	0,511			
	HRP4 ← HRP	0,77	0,593			
	HRP5 ← HRP	0,735	0,540			
Manufacturing Planning and Control	MPC1 ← MPC	0,713	0,508			
	MPC2 ← MPC	0,796	0,634			
	MPC3 ← MPC	0,774	0,599			
	MPC4 ← MPC	0,703	0,494			
	MPC5 ← MPC	0,714	0,510			
Process and Equipment	PEQ1 ← PEQ	0,729	0,531			
	PEQ2 ← PEQ	0,735	0,540			
	PEQ3 ← PEQ	0,701	0,491			
	PEQ4 ← PEQ	0,701	0,491			
	PEQ5 ← PEQ	0,778	0,605			
Supplier Relationship	SRE1 ← SRE	0,795	0,632			
	SRE2 ← SRE	0,723	0,523			
	SRE3 ← SRE	0,75	0,563			
	SRE4 ← SRE	0,708	0,501			
	SRE5 ← SRE	0,732	0,536			
Organizational Culture	OCU1 ← OCU	0,781	0,610			
	OCU2 ← OCU	0,739	0,546			
	OCU3 ← OCU	0,735	0,540			
	OCU4 ← OCU	0,794	0,630			
	OCU5 ← OCU	0,757	0,573			
	OCU6 ← OCU	0,733	0,537			
	OCU7 ← OCU	0,764	0,584			
Sustainable Performance	SPE1 ← SPE	0,721	0,520			
	SPE2 ← SPE	0,742	0,551			
	SPE3 ← SPE	0,709	0,503			
	SPE4 ← SPE	0,733	0,537			
	SPE5 ← SPE	0,825	0,681			
	SPE6 ← SPE	0,724	0,524			

Variables	Indicators	Outer Loading	Communality	Variable	R Square	GoF Index
	SPE7 ← SPE	0,825	0,681		0,631	0,596
			0,564			

Appendix 19. Goodness of Fit

Indeks	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.074	0.074
d_ULS	4.286	4.286
d_G	1.970	1.970
Chi-Square	1.496.016	1.496.016
NFI	0.609	0.609

Appendix 20. Outer Loading and Path Coefficient

